

The Multifactorial Analysis of Motivation and Workload's Effect on Employee Performance in Jajag Banyuwangi Health Center During the Covid-19 Pandemic

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Abstract:- The aims of research were to analyze the multifactorial impact of motivation and workload on the performance of employees of the Banyuwangi Jajag Health Center during the Covid-19 pandemic. The type of research was analytic observational with a cross-sectional research design. The research location was at the Banyuwangi Jajag Health Center for a period of 5 months. The population in this study were employees of the Jajag Health Center, totaling 38 people with a sample of 35 people using a simple random sampling technique. The analysis method was univariate and bivariate. The results showed that motivation had a significant impact on employee performance with a p-value of less than 0.05 and a positive correlation value or a unidirectional relationship.

Keywords:- Information, Occupational, Safety, System and Website

I. INTRODUCTION

The World Health Organization (WHO) reports that more than 28 million cases have been confirmed with more than 911,000 deaths worldwide, due to the emergence of a new type of virus in the coronavirus family called SARS-Cov-2 or more commonly called coronavirus 2019 on September 12, 2020 (Covid-19; World Health Organization, 2020). According to the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, on September 12, 2020 in America there were 159,300 health workers infected with Covid-19, 702 people died, due to a decline in health workers resulting in increased fatigue and depression in health workers (Caldas, et al., 2021). In recent months nurses and other medical personnel have worked harder than usual in handling cases of the Covid-19 pandemic. The increasing number of patients affected by the virus has forced them to work more intensively. Working hours which were originally only 6-8 hours have become more than that time and even work overtime. This causes work fatigue, which is a warning from the body that is experiencing physical and psychological decline. Work fatigue can cause work accidents. Data from the International Labor Organization (ILO) reveals that every year 2.5 million workers die due to work accidents (Musta'in et al., 2021).

The fatigue experienced by employees will affect the resulting risk, if it is not repaired properly it will be followed by decreased work performance (Tarwaka, 2013). Previous research data on nurses showed moderate physical workload rates of 45%, high 55%, moderate mental workload 62.5%, high 37.5%, where excessive workload on nurses triggers stress and burnout (Kusumaningsih, et al. ., 2020). The increasing cases of Covid-19 make work pressure higher and workloads increase which will make employees overwhelmed, difficult, and work tired. A pandemic causes uncertainty, drastic change, and circumstances that get out of control. This is a new challenge for health workers in dealing with patients infected with Covid-19.

Workload is one of the factors that affect employee performance. A high workload can improve employee performance, but an excessive workload can cause a decrease in employee performance. The inability of employees to complete work caused by the capacity and ability of employees does not match the demands that must be done (Lisnayetti & Hasanbasri, 2006). Workloads can occur if employees are unable to complete tasks according to their capacity due to excessive work demands. There is too much work to be done due to short time constraints and it could also be due to a shortage of employees in a company. Companies must be able to estimate the number of employees based on the amount of output or work that can be produced by each employee, it can be seen the number of employees actually needed by the company to achieve the target. This can be done through a work capacity measurement, so that employees can work optimally according to their abilities (Paramitadewi, 2017).

Health care workers experience a degree of psychological distress when caring for patients during a pandemic, which is highly contagious, emotional for health workers working in high-risk environments (Rose, Hartnett, & Pillai, 2021). However, the workload given to nurses may also not affect nurse job satisfaction during a pandemic because satisfaction is obtained from others such as satisfaction with salary, satisfaction with superiors and coworkers (Kirana, et al., 2021). Previous studies with the results that 90.4% of health workers require mental health care from work centers, 43.3% predict psychological care in the future and 85, 4% lack of personal protective equipment (PPE) which causes

increased stress and anxiety, hence the need for mental health care services for health workers and training during the pandemic to avoid psychological disorders (Haikan, et al., 2020). The high mental workload on health workers during the pandemic requires an implementation strategy by providing social and psychological support to moderate the mental workload and improve the performance of nurses who provide care for people with Covid-19 (Pourteimour, et al., 2020). The workload of dentists during the pandemic increases and can reduce the performance of dentists, dentists are required to use level 3 PPE (hazmat coveralls, respiratory masks, gloves, head coverings, boots) making them uncomfortable and not free to do their work (Ulfa, et al.,

Motivation is a need that encourages a person to carry out a series of activities that lead to the achievement of a certain goal. Motivation that causes, distributes and supports human behavior, so that they are willing to work hard to achieve optimal results. Motivation refers to the power that exists within a person to encourage and change the capacity to do work which becomes a desire to work, an inner state, energizes, activates, moves one's behavior in a certain direction (Avramoska, 2020). In the world of health, motivation is the process that initiates, guides, and maintains the goal of performance-oriented behavior. Every human activity requires motivation to achieve goals (Acharya & Anand, 2020). Managers must motivate employees to do and get things done on their own without being asked to do so. Extrinsic motivation is the result that is driven by external rewards such as salary, material, assets, prestige, and positive evaluation from others (Mukhtarmizi, et al., 2020). A person's work motivation in doing his job is influenced by two factors, namely internal factors that come from psychological processes within a person and external factors that come from outside a person (Environment Factors) (Sariani, 2020).

Research conducted at the Office of the Library and Archives in Bandung reported that work motivation decreased during the pandemic because of the fear of being in a crowd and the fear of working in the office. The results of research on employee work motivation from the dimensions of the need for achievement, the need for strength and the need for affiliation are in the high category (Herdani, et al., 2021). Motivation is important in work because it is expected that every health worker will work hard and be enthusiastic about achieving high productivity. According to Mangkunegara (2009), the motivation possessed by a person will largely determine the quality of behavior or work results displayed. Research by Yanti et al. (2020) found the results of good work motivation 52.8%, lack of motivation 47.2%, and the compensation received agreed 45, 1% who disagree 54.9% (Umpung, et al., 2020). Companies that implement Working from Office (WFO) during the Covid-19 pandemic provide work motivation to improve employee performance by providing employees' physiological needs and implementing health protocols (Hustia, 2020). Other research shows that work motivation has little effect on work productivity with a critical ratio value of -0.048 below the t-count value of 1.96 with P (probability) of 0.962, which means that there are still several indicators that need to be improved on the motivation variable (Haslindah, et al. al., 2020). Companies that implement Working from Office (WFO) during the Covid-19

pandemic provide work motivation to improve employee performance by providing employees' physiological needs and implementing health protocols (Hustia, 2020). Other research shows that work motivation has little effect on work productivity with a critical ratio value of -0.048 below the t-count value of 1.96 with P (probability) of 0.962, which means that there are still several indicators that need to be improved on the motivation variable (Haslindah, et al. al., 2020). Companies that implement Working from Office (WFO) during the Covid-19 pandemic provide work motivation to improve employee performance by providing employees' physiological needs and implementing health protocols (Hustia, 2020). Other research shows that work motivation has little effect on work productivity with a critical ratio value of -0.048 below the t-count value of 1.96 with P (probability) of 0.962, which means that there are still several indicators that need to be improved on the motivation variable (Haslindah, et al. al., 2020).

Employee performance is one indicator of the success of the company's operations or government agencies in achieving their goals. According to Bernadin and Rusel (in Thalib, et al., 2021) explain that the success or failure of the performance that has been achieved by a hospital is influenced by the level of performance of health workers, both individually and in groups, with the assumption that the better the performance of nurses, the better. Hopefully the hospital will get better. There are six criteria for measuring the performance of individual health workers, namely work quality, quantity of work, timeliness, effectiveness, independence, and work commitment (Santoso & Riyanto, 2020).

Covid-19 cases in the Jajag Health Center work area began to appear in August 2020, since then the Jajag Health Center has begun to form a task force team for handling Covid-19 consisting of paramedics and non-paramedics to carry out tracing and promotive activities in efforts to handle, prevent and limit infection transmission. . The formation of the Covid-19 task force team resulted in many employees having double jobs, because they had to continue to carry out their main tasks, both UKP or UKM services and carry out their duties as tracers and the Covid-19 Task Force. In addition, the adjustment to the use of the new PPE as a form of self-protection from Covid-19 transmission also adds to the burden on employees. The Covid-19 pandemic is a challenge for health workers starting from the inadequate supply of PPE, the use of PPE that causes discomfort, the threat of being infected with a virus, and the intensity of meeting family is reduced, resulting in an increased workload and increased stress levels. A study on work motivation needs to be done because during the Covid-19 pandemic, it requires work encouragement from health workers so that they can work optimally so that the role of the Puskesmas during the Covid-19 pandemic can be optimal. The high transmission power of the disease causes health workers, especially the Jajag Health Center, to be susceptible to disease. Based on this, it requires strong motivation from health workers to work. The high workload at the Jajag Health Center causes fatigue at work which has an impact on the health of health workers during the Covid-19 pandemic. Research is more focused on internal factors, external factors of motivation and workload.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESES

➤ *Relationship Between Work Motivation and Employee Performance*

According to Robbins (2010), to maximize motivation, employees need to perceive that the effort expended leads to a performance evaluation that is expected to result in a reward that is rewarded. Follow the expectancy model of motivation, if the expected goals are unclear, if the measurement criteria are vague and if the employee lacks confidence that the efforts will lead to a satisfactory appraisal of performance or believes that there will be unsatisfactory payouts by the organization if the goals are met. When performance is achieved, it can be estimated that individuals will work far below their potential.

The stronger the work motivation, the higher the employee's performance will be. This means that every increase in employee work motivation will provide a very significant increase for a very significant increase in improving employee performance in carrying out their work.

➤ *Relationship Between Workload and Employee Performance*

According to Lisnayetti and Hasanbasri (2006), a high workload is also a cause of employee dissatisfaction with their work until it eventually turns into work fatigue. The workload also has an impact on the physical and psychological so that it interferes with the performance of employees which will have a negative impact on the results of the work they do. It is better if an agency has a low or reasonable workload, so that performance will be achieved in accordance with that performance. This affects employee performance, for example in the timeliness of employees completing their work. This shows that there is an influence between workload and employee performance.

➤ *The Effect of Covid-19 Pandemic and the Workload of Healthcare Workers*

Coronaviruses are a large family of viruses that cause illness ranging from mild to severe symptoms. There are two types of coronavirus that are known to cause diseases that cause severe symptoms, such as Middle East Respiratory Syndrome (MERS) and Saver Acute Respiratory Syndrome (SARS). Coronavirus Disease 2019 (Covid-19) is a new type of disease that has never been previously identified in humans. The virus that causes Covid-19 is called Sars-CoV-2. Corona virus is zoonotic (transmitted between animals and humans). Common signs and symptoms of Covid-19 infection include symptoms of acute respiratory distress such as fever, cough and shortness of breath. The average incubation period is 5-6 days with the longest incubation period being 14 days. In severe cases of Covid-19 it can cause pneumonia, acute respiratory syndrome, kidney failure, and even death.

On January 30, 2020 WHO has declared it a Public Health Emergency of International Concern (KKMMD/PHIEC). The increase in the number of Covid-19 cases is happening quite quickly and has already spread between countries. Covid-19 can be transmitted from human to human through coughing/sneezing droplets (droplets), not through the air. People who are most at risk of contracting this disease are

people who are in close contact with Covid-19 patients, including those who care for Covid-19 patients. In an effort to contain and prevent new cases of the corona virus in Indonesia, the government has formed a task force to accelerate the handling of Covid-19. The Covid-19 Task Force is under the scope of the National Disaster Management Agency (BNPB) (Ministry of Health, 2020). The increasing workload of healthcare workers during the Covid-19 pandemic is affecting performance, causing medical errors, contributing to patient deaths and is a major concern of all healthcare organizations worldwide. The workload of health workers is one of the factors that affect performance, this is due to the inability of employees to complete treatment caused by the capacity and ability of employees not in accordance with the demands that must be done. Considering that human care is mental and physical, each has a different burden (Jahari, 2019). this is due to the inability of employees to complete treatment caused by the capacity and ability of employees not in accordance with the demands that must be done. Considering that human care is mental and physical, each has a different burden (Jahari, 2019). this is due to the inability of employees to complete treatment caused by the capacity and ability of employees not in accordance with the demands that must be done. Considering that human care is mental and physical, each has a different burden (Jahari, 2019).

The hypotheses of this study include:

Hypothesis 1: There is a significant impact between motivation on employee performance at the Banyuwangi Jajag Health Center during the Covid-19 pandemic.

Hypothesis 2: There is a significant impact between workload on employee performance at the Banyuwangi Jajag Health Center during the Covid-19 pandemic.

Hypothesis 3: There is a multifactorial impact of motivation and workload on the performance of Jajag Banyuwangi Health Center employees during the Covid-19 pandemic.

III. METHODS

This research was a quantitative research using analytical observational study method. Analytical observational method is a study without active intervention from researchers, researchers only make observations with a Cross Sectional approach, namely a research design by measuring at the same time or at one time, which aims to determine the performance of Jajag Health Center employees in the time of the Covid-19 pandemic. The location of this research was at the Banyuwangi Jajag Health Center which is located at Jalan PB. Sudirman No. 124 Jajag, Gambiran District, Banyuwangi Regency. The population were all employees of the Jajag Health Center which consisted of 38 people. The number of samples in this study using the Slovin formula. The number of samples used for this study were 35 people. Data analysis method used a Univariate analysis is an analysis used to identify and analyze existing variables (independent and dependent variables) descriptively by making a frequency distribution table.

The variables described are age, gender, last education. Then the bivariate analysis conducted on the two variables was suspected to have a relationship or influence. Further data analysis Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) was a

multivariate analysis technique that can analyze the relationship between variables in a more complex manner. This technique allows researchers to examine the relationship between manifest variables and latent variables, the relationship between one manifest variable and other latent variables and can explain measurement errors. Manifest variables are indicators used in measurement while latent variables are variables that cannot be measured directly and require several indicators (Ghozali, 2008). PLS or Partial Least Square Path Modeling.

IV. RESULT

➤ *The Analysis of Impact of Motivation on Employee Performance*

To find out the existence of a significant relationship or impact between the variables of motivation and employee performance, a bivariate test was carried out. Motivation as the independent variable (X) and employee performance as the dependent variable (Y). The bivariate test in this study used logistic regression statistical tests with the help of SPSS 26. The logistic regression test was used for data in the form of categories, namely nominal and ordinal scales (Hidayat, 2010). The following are the results of the logistic regression analysis of employee motivation and performance:

Table 1. Logistics Regression Test Results (Y)

Variable	P-values	B	Correlation	Information
Motivation (X1)	0.038	1,452	0.762	H1 Accepted
Constant	0.048	6,049		

Y = 6.049 + 1.452 X1

Based on table 1, it can be obtained information that motivation has a significant impact on employee performance. This is evidenced by the p-value which is less than 0.05. In addition, a positive correlation value indicates that the relationship between motivation and employee performance is unidirectional. That is, the higher the motivation, the higher the employee's performance. Then, the magnitude of the value of B or the regression coefficient in the regression equation shows that if the value of the workload variable is constant, then when the motivation value is increased by 1 unit, it will increase the employee's performance value by 1.452. From some of the information it can be concluded that the first hypothesis is accepted.

➤ *The Analysis of Impact of Workload on Employee Performance*

To find out the existence of a significant relationship or impact between the variables of workload and employee performance, a bivariate test was carried out. Workload as the independent variable (X) and employee performance as the dependent variable (Y). The bivariate test in this study used logistic regression statistical tests using SPSS 26. Logistic regression tests were used for data in the form of categories, namely nominal and ordinal scales (Hidayat, 2010). The

following are the results of the logistic regression analysis of Workload and Employee Performance:

Table 2. Results of Employee Performance Logistics Regression Test (Y)

Variable	P-values	B	Correlation	Information
Workload (X2)	0.042	- 1,591	-0.609	H2 Accepted
Constant	0.048	6,049		

Y = 6.049 – 1.591 X2

Table 2 can be obtained information that workload has a significant impact on employee performance. This is evidenced by the p-value which is less than 0.05. In addition, the negative correlation value indicates that the relationship between workload and employee performance is in the opposite direction. So, the higher the workload, the lower the employee's performance. Then, the magnitude of the B value or the regression coefficient in the regression equation shows that if the value of the Motivation variable is constant, the employee's performance value will decrease by 1.591 when the workload value increases by 1 unit. From this evidence, it can be concluded that the second hypothesis is accepted.

➤ *Analysis of the Multifactorial Impact of Motivation and Workload on Employee Performance*

Statistical test for more than two variables using multivariate test. In this study, the multivariate test used was PLS-SEM with the help of Smart PLS 3.0. This test aims to determine whether or not there is a significant relationship between the latent variables. Multivariate analysis can be used to analyze the relationship between variables in a more complex manner. So that research that aims to analyze the multifactorial impact of motivation and workload on employee performance can be analyzed. In the PLS-SEM test there are several stages that must be passed:

1. Outer Model Evaluation (Measurement Model)

Evaluation of the measurement model is a stage to test the validity and reliability of a construct consisting of convergent validity, discriminant validity, and construct reliability. All three will be described in detail as follows:

a) Convergent Validity Test

Convergent validity test aims to determine the respondent's understanding of the questions on each variable as intended by the researcher. Convergent validity is known through the value of loading factor and Average Variance Extracted (AVE). An instrument is said to meet the convergent validity test if it has a loading factor value of more than 0.7 (ideal). However, according to Ghozali (2006), if the loading factor value > 0.5 then convergent validity is met, if the loading factor value < 0.5 then the construct must be removed from the analysis. Meanwhile, the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value must also be more than 0.5. The results of the convergent validity test can be seen in table 3.

Table 3. Convergent Validity Test Results

Variable	Indicator	Loading Factor	AVE
X.1 Motivation	X.1.1 Compensation	0.744	0.575
	X.1.2 Achievements	0.825	
	X.1.3 The work itself	0.844	
	X.1.4 Responsibilities	0.736	
	X.1.5 Work Environment	0.567	
	X.1.6 Relations with Coworkers	0.799	
X.2 Workload	X.2.1 Physical Aspect	0.796	0.577
	X.2.2 Psychological Aspect	0.836	
	X.2.3 Aspect of Working Time	0.912	
	X.2.4 Gender	0.634	
	X.2.5 Age	0.565	
Y.1 Employee Performance	Y.1.1 Quantity	0.828	0.638
	Y.1.2 Quality	0.775	
	Y.1.3 Responsibilities	0.875	
	Y.1.4 Cooperation	0.732	
	Y.1.5 Initiative	0.774	

Based on table 3, it can be seen that all indicators generate loading factor value which is more than 0.5 even most of the value is more than 0.7. In addition, all variables also produce an Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value greater than 0.5. Thus, all indicators in this study were declared valid in measuring the variables.

b) Discriminant Validity Test

Discriminant validity was calculated using the cross loading value. If the value of cross loading in a variable that if the correlation value is greater than the cross loading value of the indicator on other variables, then the indicator is declared valid or unbiased in measuring the corresponding variable. The results of the cross loading calculation are in the following table:

Table 4. Discriminant Validity Test Results (Cross Loading)

Indicator	Workload	Performance	Motivation
Physical Aspect	0.796	-0.414	-0.252
Psychological Aspect	0.836	-0.545	-0.516
Aspect of Working Time	0.912	-0.474	-0.279
JK	0.634	-0.390	-0.068
Age	0.565	-0.039	-0.140
Quantity	-0.756	0.828	0.431
Quality	-0.281	0.775	0.527
Responsibility	-0.452	0.875	0.482
Cooperation	-0.401	0.732	0.477
Initiative	-0.261	0.774	0.514
Compensation	-0.193	0.516	0.744
Achievement	-0.273	0.571	0.825
The work itself	-0.354	0.567	0.844
Responsibility	-0.298	0.281	0.736
Work environment	-0.262	0.229	0.567
Relationship with coworkers	-0.343	0.375	0.799

Based on the results of discriminant validity in table 4, the overall indicators of each construct generate cross loading value which is greater than the value of cross loading to other constructs. Thus it can be stated that all indicators are valid because each indicator is able to measure the latent variable that corresponds well or is not biased to other variables.

c) Construct Reliability Test

Construct reliability testing is used to prove the accuracy, consistency, and accuracy of the instrument in measuring the construct (Ghozali & Latan, 2021). It can be seen based on the value of Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability. The test criteria state that Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability values greater than 0.7 indicate that the construct is reliable (Nunnally & Bernstein, 1994). The results of the calculation of Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability can be seen in the following table:

Table 5. Construct Reliability Test Results

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability
X.1 Motivation	0.857	0.889
X.2 Workload	0.820	0.869
Y.1 Employee Performance	0.858	0.898

Based on table 5, it can be seen that each variable produces Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability values greater than 0.7. Thus, all indicators can be declared reliable. That is, all indicators in this study are consistent, precise, and accurate in measuring latent variables.

Fig 1 Outer Model Construct

Figure 1 shows the magnitude of the correlation of each indicator to the latent variable. In addition, the picture above also shows the correlation value and the direction of the relationship between the independent latent variable and the dependent latent variable. Motivation has the greatest influence on employee performance in a positive manner, which is 0.453. That is, the higher the motivation will improve employee performance. On the other hand, workload has a negative effect on employee performance, which is 0.402. This means that the higher the workload, the lower the employee's performance.

2. Evaluation of Inner Model (Structural Model)

Evaluation of the structural model is the stage to evaluate the value of goodness of fit which includes the coefficient of determination and predictive relevance as well as testing the research hypothesis. This will be explained in detail as follows:

a) Coefficient of Determination (R2)

The coefficient of determination (R2) is used to measure how much strength or contribution to an association between two exogenous and endogenous variables (Haryono, 2017).

Thus, the magnitude of the effect of exogenous variables on endogenous variables can be measured. The results of R2 can be seen in the following table:

Table 6. Results of the Coefficient of Determination (R2)

Dependent Variable	R-Square
Y.1 Employee Performance	0.502

Table 6 shows the magnitude of the R-square value, namely 0.502. This shows that the diversity of endogenous variables employee performance can be explained by exogenous variables, namely motivation and workload as a whole by 50.2%. While the remaining 49.8% is the contribution of other variables not examined in this study.

b) Predictive Relevance (Q2)

The value of Q2 can be used to measure how well the observed values generated by the model and also the parameter estimates are. This approach was adapted by PLS using a blindfolding procedure. If the Q2 value is greater than 0 (zero) it indicates that the model is said to be good enough, while the Q2 value is less than 0 (zero) indicating that the model is not good or has no relevant predictive value. The following are the results of the predictive relevance test (Q2):

Table 7 Predictive Relevance Test Results (Q2)

Dependent Variable	SSO	SSE	Q ² = (1 - SSE/SSO)
Y.1 Employee Performance	175,000	126,968	0.274

Q2 predictive relevance values of 0.02, 0.15, 0.35 indicate that the model is weak, moderate, and strong (Ghozali & Latan, 2021). The results in table 4.10 show that the employee performance variable produces a predictive relevance value (Q2) greater than 0 (zero) which is 0.274. That is, the model in this study can be said to be good because it is able to explain the information in the data.

c) Hypothesis test

At this stage, the significance of the hypothesis will be tested so that it can be seen whether there is an influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable. The test criteria state that if the value of *t-statistics* *t*-table is 1.96 or *p*-value < significant alpha 5%, it can be stated that there is a significant effect between the independent variable and the dependent variable. The results of hypothesis testing can be seen from table 8.

Table 8 Hypothesis Testing Results

Influence	Coefficient	T-Statistics	P-Values
Motivation -> Performance	0.453	2,889	0.004
Workload -> Performance	-0.402	3.065	0.002

Based on table 8 it can be seen that the value of *t-statistics* Motivation on employee performance is 2.889 > 1.96 and the *p*-value is 0.004 < 0.05. This strengthens the acceptance of the first hypothesis that there is a significant

impact between motivation (X1) on employee performance (Y1) at the Jajag Health Center. In addition, the table also shows the value of *t*-statistics Workload on employee performance is $3.065 > 1.96$ and the *p*-value is $0.002 < 0.05$. This also strengthens the second hypothesis that there is a significant impact between workload (X2) on employee performance (Y1) at the Jajag Health Center.

V. DISCUSSION

➤ *Characteristics of Respondents*

The characteristics of the respondents were summarized using descriptive statistics. The majority of employees in this study were women between the ages of 31 and 40 years. This shows that the employees at the Jajag Health Center are dominated by women in the early and late adult age categories. Based on a study conducted by Caldas, et al., (2021) on health workers in the United States, demographic characteristics such as gender, age, and ethnicity have been shown to be associated with depression. Research from Karim & Tajibu, (2018) which suggests that the older you get, the more employees work better because their knowledge of work is already good. That is, the level of age may affect the results of this study. According to Tarwaka (2011: 130), gender, age, body posture, and health status are included as internal factors of workload. That is, the identity of the respondents used by researchers such as age and gender are related to this study. This condition allows the emergence of different results if the majority of respondents are male. This is in line with research Pourteimour, et al. (2021) in Iran, older male nurses gave high performance during the Covid-19 pandemic. According to Robbins & Judge, (2013) in a meta-analysis study found that women scored slightly higher than men on performance measures. This indicates that different results will appear if the majority of respondents are male.

The third characteristic of respondents is the last education they have. Most of the employees at the Jajag Health Center have a D-III education history. Education is an important factor in determining the work ability of employees (Wita et al., 2017). Meanwhile, according to Afandi (2018: 86), ability is one of the factors that affect employee performance. Research conducted by Sariyani, et al. (2020) also revealed that employees whose education level is mostly high school with a percentage of 69.8% still have high work motivation in themselves because they are valued by their leaders so that they use their education to the fullest.

Fig 2. Inner Model Construct

Based on Figure 4.5, it is known that the *t*-statistical values of all indicators in the variables are summarized in table 4.12. The magnitude of the *t*-statistics of all indicators on employee performance is more than *t*-table 1.96. So it can be concluded that indirectly there is a significant impact on employee performance variables or there is a multifactorial impact on motivation (X1) and workload (X2) variables on employee performance (Y1) at the Jajag Health Center. Thus it can be stated that the third hypothesis is accepted.

Table 9 Result of *t*-statistics

Hypothesis	Results	Information
H3 Multifactorial Impact of Motivation and Workload on Employee Performance at the Jajag Health Center	<i>T</i> -Statistical indicators > 1.96	Accepted

➤ *Overview of Employee Motivation, Workload, and Performance*

After the three variables in this study were analyzed descriptively, the results showed that most of the respondents had not received good work motivation. Then, the results of the analysis also show that the workload conditions experienced by most of the respondents during the Covid-19 pandemic were not good. This is not in line with research conducted by Kirana, et al. (2021) that the workload assigned to the nursing team Covid-19 does not affect motivation because motivation is obtained from other things such as physiological needs that have been met (food needs and incentives). However, employee performance shows a good category. This shows that the Covid-19 pandemic is not an obstacle for employees at the Jajag Health Center to consistently provide good service.

Figure 9 also shows the most dominant indicator in reflecting the motivation variable, namely Achievement of 6.393. Then in the workload variable there is an indicator of the psychological aspect that best reflects the construct, which is 7.190. Furthermore, the indicator that best reflects the employee performance variable is Quantity, which is 12.212.

As the theory explained earlier, the importance of motivation for someone who works has an effect on his performance. A person will tend to maximize his potential at work when there is support both inside and outside him. So that work targets will be more likely to be achieved. However, the results of the study actually showed different results. Although the motivation received by employees has not been good, Jajag Health Center employees still produce good performance during the Covid-19 pandemic. This illustrates that the employees at the Jajag Health Center always focus on their tasks and are not affected by the heavy workload and lack of motivation.

➤ *The Analysis of Impact of Motivation on Employee Performance*

The results of testing the first hypothesis prove that motivation has a significant impact on employee performance. Both have a positive or unidirectional relationship. That is, the greater the motivation, the employee's performance also increases. The results of this study are the same as the results of research conducted by Fadli & Hasanudin (2020) that motivation has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. This shows that people will tend to work harder and produce maximum output when there is good motivation from outside and inside. Similarly, research by Talib, et al. (2021) which revealed that the more motivated the nurses were to their work, the more optimal the performance would be. The results of multivariate research on the inner model construct also show that achievement is the most dominant indicator in reflecting motivation than other indicators. Someone who gets praise, awards, or allowances after working hard can stimulate his work spirit (Hasibuan, 2013: 149). The provision of proportional incentives according to their work is expected for employees to have work discipline and high motivation so as to produce high productivity as well. This is in line with Yanti .'s research The provision of proportional incentives according to their work is expected for employees to have work discipline and high motivation so as to produce high productivity as well. This is in line with Yanti .'s research Providing incentives proportionally according to their work, it is expected that employees have work discipline and high motivation so as to produce high productivity as well. This is in line with Yanti .'s research, et al. (2020) which states that the majority of nurses agree that the compensation received will affect performance for the better. The incentive system shows the clearest relationship between compensation and job performance.

In addition, the cooperation between good medical personnel will also be a good motivation to achieve good performance as well. This is supported by research conducted by Hartono & Rahardi (2021), when WFH employees feel disturbed because of difficulties communicating with their co-workers, these social needs should be met. This need is included in the five hierarchical classification of human needs according to Abraham H. Maslow with his hierarchy theory. Furthermore, an indicator that is also important is a good work environment. According to Hasibuan (2013:149), the work environment is an indirect motivation for employees. In line with research conducted by Kristina, et al. (2021) who reported that to improve the performance of good employees it is necessary to pay attention to the work environment and the

provision of adequate salaries to improve positive performance.

➤ *The Analysis of Impact of Workload on Employee Performance*

The results of testing the second hypothesis prove that workload has a significant impact on employee performance. Then, the negative sign on the correlation value indicates the opposite relationship. This means that the higher the workload, the lower the employee's performance. However, the results of research from Nabawi, R. (2019) show that the workload coefficient is positive, which means that the workload increases, employee performance also increases. Furthermore, the inner model construct shows that the psychological aspect is the most dominant indicator that reflects the workload rather than the indicators that reflect the workload. other. The increasing number of Covid-19 cases every day makes the demands for jobs that come more and more. According to Tarwaka (2011: 130), the workload on the psychological aspect can be in the form of motivation, satisfaction, desire, and perception. Satisfaction in the form of work, wages, and the work environment contributes in influencing the workload of employees. This is in line with the results of research proposed by Irawati & Carrollina, (2017) that external workloads in the form of tasks, work environment, and work attitudes have a negative effect on employee performance.

However, referring to the results of descriptive analysis, the workload of employees at the Jajag Health Center which is classified as not good still produces good employee performance. This is in line with research conducted by Astuti, & Lesmana, (2018), a high workload does not burden nurses but can actually improve performance because the ability of nurses is in accordance with work standards. Thus, it can be concluded that employees at the Jajag Health Center have good work standards so that the Covid-19 pandemic does not become an obstacle to producing good performance.

➤ *The Analysis of Multifactorial Impact of Motivation and Workload on Employee Performance*

The results of testing the fourth hypothesis prove that there is a multifactorial impact of motivation and workload on employee performance. Indirectly, every indicator in the construct or latent variable of Motivation and Workload affects employee performance. That is, without collecting data, it becomes a latent variable even though each indicator in the construct affects employee performance. Based on the bivariate test also shows that all indicators in motivation and workload have a relationship with employee performance.

First, related to the motivation variable which consists of several indicators such as compensation and achievement. Based on research Yanti, et al. (2020) shows that most respondents strongly agree that the compensation received will affect their performance. Meanwhile, achievement indicators can be seen from the provision of incentives in accordance with the proportion of work. Every performance is expected to have an incentive or reward, otherwise every incentive must be based on performance (Yanti, et al. 2020). Then, in Motivation there are other indicators such as the work itself and the work environment. When someone carries out their duties with working conditions that make them safe and

comfortable, it becomes an impetus for that person to complete their duties. Providing job guarantees to employees both in terms of workplace, insurance, and being employed in proportion to foster a sense of security. This was stated by Abraham H. Maslow in his hierarchical theory of the five hierarchies of human needs. Based on research conducted by Umpung, et al. (2020) on health workers at the Southeast Minahasa Health Center stated that a sense of security and comfort in the workplace is quite helpful in carrying out work. This research is also in line with research conducted by Hustia, (2020) whose results state that companies must create a sense of security by preparing adequate work facilities, maximum machines, and tools related to health protocols such as preparing a place for washing hands, preparing hand sanitizer, and ensure that every employee present wears a mask so that the employee's focus is only on achieving their job, not their fear of being exposed to Covid-19. Furthermore, the last indicator of motivation is the relationship with colleagues. Relationships between humans in the work environment both vertically and horizontally affect work discipline which certainly affects their performance. As the results of research stated by Umpung, et al. (2020) that interpersonal relationships between health workers aim to make communication effective in solving patient health problems. Relationships between humans in the work environment both vertically and horizontally affect work discipline which certainly affects their performance. As the results of research stated by Umpung, et al. (2020) that interpersonal relationships between health workers aim to make communication effective in solving patient health problems. Relationships between humans in the work environment both vertically and horizontally affect work discipline which certainly affects their performance. As the results of research stated by Umpung, et al. (2020) that interpersonal relationships between health workers aim to make communication effective in solving patient health problems.

Second, the relationship between all indicators of workload and employee performance. Workload is proven to have a significant impact on employee performance. Age and gender are internal factors that are quite important in influencing a person's performance. For professional employees, satisfaction will continue to increase with age, on the contrary, for non-professional employees, the level of satisfaction will decrease in middle age and then increase again in the following years. While on employee performance there is a belief that performance declines with increasing age (Robbins & Judge, 2013). Then, other indicators of workload such as physical aspects, psychological aspects, and aspects of working time are interrelated with each other and this can arise due to the demands of work that are imposed on employees. Timeliness in achieving work targets will affect employee performance in terms of quantity and quality. Because the physiological needs of employees such as working hours and rest hours affect employee health, especially during the Covid-19 pandemic (Hustia, 2020). When employees feel burdened by this, both physically and psychologically, their work will turn into work fatigue (Lisnayetti & Hasanbasri, 2006). However, several studies have shown the opposite result. Research conducted by Talib, et al. (2021) on employees of Primaya Hospital, North Bekasi, shows that workload has a positive and significant effect on performance. The nurse's

ability and knowledge helps her to treat patients so that her performance is maintained. However, the important thing to achieve is a balance between the individual and his care. In another study, it was also stated that a high workload does not burden nurses but can actually improve performance because the ability of nurses is in accordance with work standards (Astuti & Lesmana, 2018). Meanwhile, in research conducted by Irawati & Carrollina (2017), internal workloads such as age, health condition, motivation, and satisfaction have a positive effect on employee performance and external workloads such as tasks, work attitudes, and work environment have a negative effect on employee performance. In another study, it was also stated that a high workload does not burden nurses but can actually improve performance because the ability of nurses is in accordance with work standards (Astuti & Lesmana, 2018). Meanwhile, in research conducted by Irawati & Carrollina (2017), internal workloads such as age, health condition, motivation, and satisfaction have a positive effect on employee performance and external workloads such as tasks, work attitudes, and work environment have a negative effect on employee performance. In another study, it was also stated that a high workload does not burden nurses but can actually improve performance because the ability of nurses is in accordance with work standards (Astuti & Lesmana, 2018). Meanwhile, in research conducted by Irawati & Carrollina (2017), internal workloads such as age, health condition, motivation, and satisfaction have a positive effect on employee performance and external workloads such as tasks, work attitudes, and work environment have a negative effect on employee performance.

This study has limitations, including 1) The limited sample size of only 35 people was deemed insufficient to obtain detailed research results. In addition, this research was only carried out at the Jajag Health Center so that it would allow different results if carried out in different places and with different objects. However, this is sufficient to describe the state of the Jajag Health Center employees during the Covid-19 pandemic; 2) this study only uses two independent variables so that there are many other factors that can affect the performance of Jajag Health Center employees in working during the Covid-19 pandemic. It has also been proven by the coefficient of determination of 50.2% and the remaining 49.8% is influenced by other variables not examined.

VI. CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Based on the results of the analysis and hypothesis testing of 35 employees at the Jajag Health Center, it can be concluded that 1) The results describe the characteristics of the employees of the Jajag Banyuwangi Health Center, most of whom are female, aged between 31 to 40 years and have a DIII education history; 2) The results of the descriptive analysis illustrate that most of the respondents have not received good work motivation, then the workload is also classified as not good, but the employee performance shows a good category. This means that the lack of motivation obtained and the workload during the Covid-19 pandemic did not reduce the performance of Jajag Health Center employees; 3) There is a significant impact between motivation and employee performance. The greater the motivation obtained will improve the performance of the employees of the Banyuwangi

Jajag Health Center during the Covid-19 pandemic; 4) There is a significant impact between Workload and Employee Performance. The greater the workload received will reduce the performance of Jajag Banyuwangi Health Center employees during the Covid-19 pandemic and 5) There is a multifactorial impact of Motivation and Workload on the Performance of Banyuwangi Jajag Health Center employees during the Covid-19 pandemic. Indirectly, the indicators in the latent variable affect employee performance without having to measure it together with other indicators in one latent variable. The greater the workload received will reduce the performance of Jajag Banyuwangi Health Center employees during the Covid-19 pandemic and 5) There is a multifactorial impact of Motivation and Workload on the Performance of Banyuwangi Jajag Health Center employees during the Covid-19 pandemic. Indirectly, the indicators in the latent variable affect employee performance without having to measure it together with other indicators in one latent variable. The greater the workload received will reduce the performance of Jajag Banyuwangi Health Center employees during the Covid-19 pandemic and 5) There is a multifactorial impact of Motivation and Workload on the Performance of Banyuwangi Jajag Health Center employees during the Covid-19 pandemic. Indirectly, the indicators in the latent variable affect employee performance without having to measure it together with other indicators in one latent variable.

Suggestions that can be put forward include 1) Improving research on motivation, workload and employee performance in further research. This is intended to minimize weaknesses and increase existing strengths so that the results of research conducted can contribute to the development of human resource management science; 2) For puskesmas, Improving good work motivation for employees so that they can balance the existing workload and make the results of this research as a reference in making decisions and determining policies for employees. This is done so that the human resources at the Jajag Health Center remain of good quality and can maintain consistently good performance; 3) For academics to increase accuracy and critical thinking in analyzing existing problems by using this research as a reference. It is hoped that students who want to research further can develop existing theories with new findings considering that there are still other factors that affect employee performance and 5) researchers can take the results of this research into consideration in working, especially in the health sector. For example, such as increasing self-motivation and minimizing the workload faced so that it can produce good and accountable work quality. It is hoped that students who want to research further can develop existing theories with new findings considering that there are still other factors that affect employee performance and 5) researchers can take the results of this research into consideration in working, especially in the health sector. For example, such as increasing self-motivation and minimizing

the workload faced so that it can produce good and accountable work quality.

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